

Reactivity of the Methylene Group in Coumarin-3-acetic Acids. Condensation with Aromatic Aldehydes.

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It has been shown that coumarin-4 acetic acids resemble malonic acid in decomposing smoothly and quantitatively into 4-methylcoumarins and carbon dioxide at their melting points, and in having a reactive methylene group (Dey and Row, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 107, 277 ; 1925, 2, 227 ; Dey and Seshadri, *ibid.*, 1931, 8, 247). Attention was also drawn in the course of these investigations to certain remarkable colour changes which occurred when the products of condensation of a coumarin-4 acetic acid with *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde or vanillin were treated with alkali and the view was expressed that the phenomenon was presumably due to the facility with which molecules of these compounds could tautomerise into forms which were quinonoid both in the pyrone and in the second benzene nuclei (Dey and Row, *loc. cit.*). A study of the behaviour of similar products obtained from coumarin 3 acetic acids (Dey and Sankaranarayanan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 817) was expected to throw further light on the subject and justify or correct the explanations previously offered.

A comparison of the activities of methylene groups in phenylacetic and coumarin-4 acetic acids has shown the latter to be more reactive, and on grounds similar to those discussed before (*cf.* Dey and Row, *loc. cit.*), it may be argued that the activity of this group in coumarin-3 acetic acids is lower than that in the 4-acetic acids. Thus, while the 4-acetic acids and their ethyl esters condensed easily with aldehydes under the conditions of both the Perkin and the Knoevenagel reactions, coumarin-3-acetic acids could be made to react only by Perkin's method, no condensation occurring when their esters were treated with aldehydes in the presence of piperidine in the usual way. This reduction of activity may be attributed to the influence of the crotonoid system in the coumarin ring, the positive charge of the 4-C atom being expected to strengthen the tendency for ionisation of the $\text{CH}_2\text{—H}$ atoms, while the potential depletion of

electrons of the 3-C atom might have a feeble inhibiting effect on this tendency (*cf.* Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 777).

The same arguments may be advanced to explain the interesting observation that coumarin-3-acetic acids with a methyl group in position-4, fail to react with aldehydes. The influence of the methyl group is to neutralise the charge of the 4-C atom thus causing a definite and permanent electron deficit in carbon atom-3, and the consequent inhibition of activity of the CH_2 group attached to this atom. These changes seem to provide, therefore, interesting examples of electromeric polarisation resulting from the crotonoid system of the α -pyrone ring.

In contrast with the behaviour of the 4-acetic acids which yielded only coumarylphenylethylenes by this reaction, the products obtained from coumarin-3-acetic acids consisted mainly of the ethylene carboxylic acids which suffered little or no decomposition into CO_2 during the process. The compounds, in which the presence of the carboxyl group has been clearly proved, do not, however, dissolve in cold sodium carbonate and attempts to esterify them under the usual conditions were also unsuccessful; on the other hand, they were readily soluble in cold caustic soda only, unchanged material being precipitated on acidification, and they could be titrated with baryta, the results being in good agreement with the molecular weights of the monocarboxylic acids. An explanation of these interesting observations may be found in the results recently obtained by Linstead (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 115) from a study of the lactonisation of Δ^α - and Δ^β -unsaturated acids. If we accept his view that these unsaturated acids readily change into lactone systems, the process of lactonisation involving an addition reaction in which the components of the carboxyl group, H and $\text{R}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{O}$, become attached to the olefinic centre, then these coumarylethylene carboxylic acids having one of the two olefinic bonds in the β -position with respect to the COOH should be capable of lactonising rapidly according to the following scheme:

It is believed, therefore, that the acids exist chiefly in the form of the saturated lactones which are sufficiently stable to resist the action of sodium carbonate but are converted by alkali into the salts of the free acids, from the solutions of which the original lactones only are reprecipitated on acidification, thus:

The alternative view that the action of alkalis entails a fission of the pyrone and not of the new lactone ring, as interpreted in the following scheme, is equally plausible.

The products of condensation of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and vanillin with coumarin-3 acetic acids exhibited, contrary to expectation, the same colour changes when treated with alkali, though in a somewhat less intense form, as the analogous products derived from the coumarin-4-acetic acids. They dissolved immediately in cold caustic soda with a vivid red colour which faded rapidly (about 3 minutes) to a pale yellow tint. If the red solution be quickly acidified, the unchanged material is thrown down immediately, while on acidifying the pale yellow solution a white turbidity appeared followed by the slow separation of the original product; these changes are strictly parallel to those observed in the case of the corresponding 4-coumaryl-*p*-hydroxy-

phenylethylene derivatives and are obviously due to the same causes. The *p*-methoxy and *p*-acetoxy derivatives and also the *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde condensation product, like the corresponding derivatives of coumarin-4-acetic acids, behaved normally and did not exhibit any characteristic changes of colour on dissolution in alkali. We assume, therefore, that the 3-coumaryl-*p*-hydroxyphenylethylene derivatives, like their 4-analogues, tautomerise readily in the presence of alkalis into quinonoid forms which, however, revert to the normal structure through the opening of the pyrone ring by prolonged contact with alkali. The complete cycle of changes would be represented by the following scheme :

It will be seen that the structures suggested for the tautomeric forms of the products in the two cases differ in one respect: while the 4-coumaryl derivative is supposed to become *para*-quinonoid in both the rings (*cf.* Dey and Row, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 8, 280), the benzene and the pyrone rings are *para*- and *ortho*-quinonoid respectively in the case of the other product.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenyl-3-coumarylethylene Carboxylic Acid.

The dry sodium salt of coumarin-3-acetic acid (3 g.), freshly distilled benzaldehyde (1.4 g.) and acetic anhydride (12 g.) were heated in a flask under reflux at 160° for 5 hours. The product was thrown into water (100 c.c.), boiled for 5 minutes to decompose the excess of acetic anhydride and the pale red oil which separated was left in contact with water for 12 hours when it solidified to a hard brittle mass. This was crushed with water and purified by reprecipitating from dilute caustic soda. Two crystallisations from alcohol (charcoal) gave colourless tiny plates, m.p. 262°, yield 1.4 g. (Found: C, 73.47; H, 4.35. Equiv., 286.4. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 73.98; H, 4.11 per cent. Equiv., 292.0).

p-Acetoxyphenyl-3-coumarylethylene Carboxylic Acid.

Coumarin-3-sodium acetate (3 g.) and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1.7 g.) were condensed by heating with acetic anhydride (12 g.) in the usual manner and the solid product obtained by pouring into water was collected and left in contact with dilute alkali for some hours. Most of the substance dissolved leaving a residue (0.3 g. approximately) melting rather indefinitely between 140° and 150°, which was proved to be the decarboxylated product (*vide infra*). The pale yellow filtrate was acidified and the voluminous precipitate collected and crystallised twice from glacial acetic acid in small colourless plates, m.p. 244° (decomp.), yield 1.3 g. (Found:

C, 69.5; H, 4.07. Equiv., 355. $C_{20}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 68.6; H, 4.0 per cent. Equiv., 350).

p-Acetoxyphenyl-3-coumarylethylene.—The small amount of the residue insoluble in alkali obtained from the condensation of coumarin-3-sodium acetate and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol in short pale yellow needles, m.p. 165°, yield 0.15 g. (Found: C, 74.5; H, 4.3. $C_{19}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 74.5; H, 4.5 per cent).

p-Hydroxyphenyl-3-coumarylethylene carboxylic acid was prepared from the acetoxy compound by boiling with 2*N*-alkali for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and crystallising the yellow precipitate which was thrown on acidification from boiling methanol as yellow needles, m.p. 272° (decomp.). (Found: C, 70.1; H, 3.92. Equiv., 313. $C_{18}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 70.1; H, 3.90 per cent. Equiv., 308).

p-Hydroxyphenyl-3-coumarylethylene was prepared by the hydrolysis of the acetoxy derivative (m.p. 165°) in the usual way. It crystallised from acetic acid in golden yellow needles, m.p. 227°. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 4.66. $C_{17}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 77.27; H, 4.54 per cent).

A list of similar compounds prepared by condensing coumarin-3-acetic acids with various aromatic aldehydes under the same conditions is given in the following table.

Name.	M.p.	Appearance.	Analysis.	Mode of formation.
1. <i>m</i> -Acetoxyphenyl-3-coumarylethylene carboxylic acid	188°	Colourless plates	Equiv., 356.7. $C_{20}H_{14}O_6$ requires Equiv., 350.	Coumarin-3-sodium acetate and <i>m</i> -hydroxybenzaldehyde
2. <i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl-3-coumarylethylene carboxylic acid	242°	Colourless cubes	...	Hydrolysis of (1)
3. <i>m</i> -Acetoxyphenyl-3-coumarylethylene	140°	Pale yellow plates	C, 74.8; H, 4.4. $C_{19}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 74.5; H, 4.5 %.	By-product in the preparation of 1; insoluble in NaOH
4. <i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl-3-coumarylethylene	193°	Colourless rectangular plates	...	Hydrolysis of (3)
5. 3-Coumaryl-3'-methoxy-4'-acetoxyphenylethylene carboxylic acid	207°	Colourless cubes	Equiv., 383.1. $C_{21}H_{16}O_7$ requires Equiv., 380.	Coumarin-3-sodium acetate and vanillin
6. 3-Coumaryl-3'-methoxy-4'-hydroxyphenylethylene carboxylic acid	211°	Yellow cubes	C, 67.4; H, 4.2. $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 67.46; H, 4.14 %.	Hydrolysis of (5); also from coumarin-3-acetic acid and vanillin (Knoevenagel)

Name.	M.p.	Appearance.	Analysis.	Mode of formation.
7. 3-Coumaryl-4'-methoxyphenylethylene carboxylic acid	225°	Colourless plates	C, 70.5; H, 4.03. $C_{19}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 70.8; H, 4.35%.	Coumarin-3-sodium acetate and anisaldehyde
8. Methylene ether of 3':4'-dihydroxyphenyl-3-coumaryl ethylene carboxylic acid	270°	Micro-needles	C, 68.4; H, 3.68. $C_{19}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 67.9; H, 3.57%.	Coumarin-3-sodium acetate and piperonal
9. 7-Acetoxy-4-methyl-3-coumaryl-3'-coumarin	268°	Colourless prisms	C, 69.0; H, 3.97. $C_{21}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 69.6; H, 3.90%.	7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin-3-sodium acetate and salicylaldehyde
10. 7:7'-Diacetoxy-4-methyl-3:3'-dicoumarin	220°	Colourless plates	C, 65.32; H, 3.61. $C_{23}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 65.72; H, 3.81%	7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin-3-sodium acetate and resorcylic aldehyde
11. 7-Acetoxy-4-methyl-3-coumaryl-3'- β -1:2-naphthapyrone	272°	Rectangular plates	C, 72.8; H, 3.94. $C_{25}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 72.8; H, 3.85%.	7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin-3-sodium acetate and β -naphthol aldehyde
12. β -Naphtha-3-coumarylphenylethylene carboxylic acid	253°	Yellow prismatic needles	Equiv., 341.8. $C_{22}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 342.	β -1:2-Naphthapyrone-3-sodium acetate and benzaldehyde
13. 3:3'-Di- β -naphthapyrone	345°	Golden yellow needles	C, 79.27; H, 3.79. $C_{26}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 80.0; H, 3.59%.	β -1:2-Naphthapyrone-3-acetic acid and β -naphthol aldehyde

